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Research Article

**DEVELOPING ASSESSMENT TOOLS FOR PLASTIC
SURGERY IN SAUDI ARABIA**¹Lamyaa Omar Al-Gelban¹Medical intern, faculty of medicine, King Khalid University**Abstract**

Background: Currently, in Saudi Arabia, plastic surgery-based education relies heavily on traditional, time-based training models. The objective of this study is to develop a methodology to determine the basic procedural steps for plastic surgery procedures to assist the training and evaluation of evaluators as well.

Aim: The aim of this study was to develop a methodology to determine the basic procedural steps for plastic surgery procedures to assist the training and evaluation of evaluators as well.

Methods: This study is a cross-sectional study. The data was collected using an online questionnaire answered by heads of plastic surgery departments. The sample size in this analysis was 120 individuals. The data was collected and analyzed using SPSS version 22.

Results: Around 31% of the sample think that there is an increasing need to address this deficit in order to meet today's training standards, while 34% think the opposite. Only 27.5% confirmed that there is no formal or objective assessment of technical skills among trainees in plastic surgery, while 35.8% confirmed there is an objective assessment. Around 27% of the sample agree that procedural skills can be assessed during actual care delivery, while 36% have the opposite opinion.

Conclusion: The best curriculum should provide exposure to core principles of plastic surgery while demonstrating competence through performance of index procedures. Accordingly, it is recommended that exploring the role and potential benefits of competency-based medical education in plastic surgery residency training is timely.

Keywords: Assessment Tools, Plastic Surgery, Saudi Arabia

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INTRODUCTION:

Currently, in Saudi Arabia, plastic surgery-based education relies heavily on traditional, time-based training models. [1]

As in most other surgical specialties, success is measured by self-defined performance assessments and completion of a knowledge-based test. There is no formal or objective assessment of technical skills among trainees in plastic surgery. [2]

In practice, procedural skills can be assessed during actual care delivery; however, this may not always be possible. [3]

Due to the large number of procedures performed by cosmetic surgeons in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, the evaluation of each skill in a procedural manner will not be realistic unless the evaluation process is not facilitated, because it is important in Saudi Arabia to develop high quality tools for the main procedures that explain the best understand to the wide range of principles of plastic surgery that are necessary for specialization. [4]

Once identified, these key actions, including their many efficiencies and stages, can be evaluated using objective assessment tools that will achieve recognition that the trainee should be qualified to perform multiple actions at a specific level of supervision, ranging from observation to independent practice. [5]

Several previous studies have dealt with the same idea in detail, through the study of objective tools to assess the procedural skills in residency training plastic surgery is currently lacking. There is an

increasing need to address this deficit in order to meet today's training standards in North America.

The purpose of this study was to develop a methodology to determine the basic procedural steps for plastic surgery procedures to assist the training and evaluation of evaluators as well.

PATIENTS AND METHODS:

This study is a descriptive cross sectional study. The study sample is 120 Cosmetic surgery surgeons in Saudi Arabia. The sample covered all different ages and experience, in addition to all genders.

The study was conducted over the hospitals all over the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia. The study extended for one year from 1/11/2017 to 1/11/2018.

The data was collected through the internet using an online questionnaire directed to the targeted sample. The data was then entered and analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 22.

RESULTS:

The data was collected using an online survey from the heads of general plastic surgery departments. The sample size was 120 individuals. It was clarified that the questions are covering the basic general plastic surgery.

When the sampled individuals were asked if "The development of evaluation tools for plastic surgery is one of the things that needs continuous development", 78.3% agreed, while 21.7% disagreed with the statement as shown in table 1.

Table 1: Opinion of participating doctors if the development of evaluation tools for plastic surgery is one of the things that needs continuous development.

Answer	Frequency	Percent
No	26	21.7%
Yes	94	78.3%
Total	120	100.0

Around 31% of the sample think that there is an increasing need to address this deficit in order to meet today's training standards, while 34% think the opposite as shown in table 2.

Table 2: opinion of participating doctors about the need to address the deficit in plastic surgery field in order to meet today's training standards?

Answer	Frequency	Percent
No	41	34.2
Yes	37	30.8
May be	42	35.0
Total	120	100.0

More importantly, 35% reported that in Saudi Arabia, plastic surgery-based education does not rely heavily on traditional, time-based training models. On the other hand, approximately 32% reported the opposite as shown in table 3.

Table 3: opinion of participating doctors if plastic surgery-based education relies heavily on traditional, time-based training models in Saudi Arabia or not.

Answer	Frequency	Percent
No	42	35.0
Yes	38	31.7
May be	40	33.3
Total	120	100.0

58.3% of the sampled individuals reported that in surgical specialties, success is measured by self-defined performance assessments and completion of a knowledge-based test. However, 41.7% reported the opposite as shown in table 4.

Table 4: opinion of participating doctors if success is measured by self-defined performance assessments and completion of a knowledge-based test.

Answer	Frequency	Percent
No	50	41.7
Yes	70	58.3
Total	120	100.0

Only 27.5% confirmed that there is no formal or objective assessment of technical skills among trainees in plastic surgery, while 35.8% confirmed that there is an objective assessment as shown in table 5.

Table 5: opinion of participating doctors about the absence of formal or objective assessment of technical skills among trainees in plastic surgery.

Answer	Frequency	Percent
No	43	35.8
Yes	33	27.5
May be	44	36.7
Total	120	100.0

Around 27% of the sample agree that procedural skills can be assessed during actual care delivery, while 36% have the opposite opinion as shown in table 6.

Table 6: opinion of participating doctors if Procedural skills can be assessed during actual care delivery

Answer	Frequency	Percent
No	43	35.8
Yes	32	26.7
May be	45	37.5
Total	120	100.0

About 31% of the sample see that cosmetic surgery is not widespread in KSA, while 33% see that it has been widespread as shown in table 7.

Table 7: opinion of participating doctors if cosmetic surgery is widespread in Saudi Arabia or not.

Answer	Frequency	Percent
No	37	30.8
Yes	39	32.5
May be	44	36.7
Total	120	100.0

Surprisingly, only 37.5% of the sample think that it is important in Saudi Arabia to develop high-quality tools for the main procedures of plastic surgery as shown in table 8.

Table 8: opinion of participating doctors if it is important in Saudi Arabia to develop high-quality tools for the main procedures of plastic surgery.

Answer	Frequency	Percent
No	34	28.3
Yes	45	37.5
May be	41	34.2
Total	120	100.0

The majority of the sample (80%) see that it is important for surgeons to have a better understanding of the wide range of principles of plastic surgery necessary for specialization as shown in table 9.

Table 9: opinion of participating doctors if it is important for surgeons to have a better understanding of the wide range of principles of plastic surgery necessary for specialization.

Answer	Frequency	Percent
No	24	20.0
Yes	96	80.0
Total	120	100.0

55.8% of the sampled surgeons see that an apprentice (plastic surgery) should be qualified to perform multiple tasks at a specified level of supervision as shown in table 10.

Table 10: opinion of participating doctors if an apprentice (plastic surgery) should be qualified to perform multiple tasks at a specified level of supervision.

Answer	Frequency	Percent
No	53	44.2
Yes	67	55.8
Total	120	100.0

DISCUSSION:

The aim of this study is to develop a methodology to determine the basic procedural steps for plastic surgery procedures. Due to the great number of plastic surgery procedures and the implausibility of assessing each one individually, a set of questions was directed to measure or predetermine the needed skills level for the plastic surgeons to have. However, other relevant studies that tackled the same topic were specified and focused on a specific type of plastic surgery such as breast surgery.

CONCLUSION:

The best teaching method should provide exposure to core and basic principles of plastic surgery while demonstrating competence through performance of index procedures. These procedures are most likely to benefit graduating students when entering independent practice and span all domains of plastic surgery.

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